

ANALYSIS OF MORPHOLOGY AND SYNTAX PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS USING A WEBQUEST-BASED TEACHING STRATEGY AT IGNATIUS AJURU UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION, RIVERS STATE

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Abstract

This study analyzed the performance of students in morphology and syntax using WebQuest-based teaching strategy at Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State. A quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test non-equivalent group design was used. The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. The sample consisted of 280 year two students drawn from a population of 1,203 year two students from the Faculty of Humanities, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were used to select the samples. The research instrument for data collection was a 40-item multiple-choice test questions on morphology and syntax validated by one senior lecturer in language education and two experts in measurement and evaluation. Kuder-Richardson 21 was used to calculate the reliability, and a coefficient of 0.84 was obtained. Mean, standard deviation, and percentage were used to analyze the research questions, whereas analysis of variance and t-test were used to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught morphology and syntax using the WebQuest-based teaching strategy. In addition, there was no significant difference in the interaction effect of gender and teaching method on the mean morphology and syntax performance score of undergraduate students in both the treatment (WebQuest) and control groups. It was recommended that morphology and syntax should be taught to undergraduate students using the WebQuest design teaching strategy because it enhanced the performance of both male and female students.

Introduction

WebQuest is a scaffolded learning strategy that uses links to essential resources on the World Wide Web (WWW) and authentic tasks to motivate students' investigation of a central, open-ended question and participation in a final group process that attempts to transform acquired information into a more sophisticated form (March, 2015). WebQuest is a web-based activity that requires students to be active learners and allows them to enhance their higher-order thinking skills, such as finding topic-related web sites and examining and selecting well-prepared and reliable web sites (Halat, 2018).

The 21st century has witnessed new challenges and demands in Nigerian society. These challenges have proven that there is a higher level of competitiveness to accomplish goals successfully in this globalized world. Hence, using technological resources such as the Internet and computers has become crucial for attaining a complete education process (Orozco & Marin, 2017). Moreover, technology is one of the most important language aids for students to build confidence and facilitate learning. EL-Khateeb (2016) stated that the Internet is among the most important tools for teaching the English language, where teachers benefit as they provide support in gaining teaching techniques and approaches. Students are also beneficiaries from internet sites, as these facilitate the student-centered learning process and widen their knowledge span. Using computers in the education process increases students' academic performance, motivating lessons, and encouraging students to study cooperatively. One of the roots of the constructivist approach is WebQuest, which enables the performance of research-based activities, enables students to practice, and promotes high thinking ability (Lahaie, 2018). WebQuests offer good Internet-based language learning opportunities because they provide learners with exposure to authentic material, meaningful content, and possibilities for real communication in the target language. Considering the important role of morphology and syntax in critical reading in students' academic and personal lives and considering the benefits derivable from the application of critical reading lessons in EFL classrooms and the growing use of WebQuests as collaborative web tools that could be implemented in critical reading classrooms, WebQuest should be used to develop students' critical reading performance. Students should be more concerned about developing their reading and writing skills and, hence, improve their English language performance. Hence, technology should be used in the process of learning the English language subject, as it helps improve students' performance in the subject.

Statement of the problem

Despite advances in educational technology and basic educational research, teaching and learning in Nigeria continue to experience challenges in the acquisition of functional education. However, information and communication technologies have gained more positive impact on the educational development of students and teachers around the globe. The focus is on ways in which technology can be used to support instructional delivery and students' achievement in education. In support of this, Onasanya, Fakomogbon, Sheu, and Soetan (2016) maintained that the integration of emerging technology platforms in the teaching and learning process has become crucial as they play a significant role in the advancement of knowledge. For example, information and communication technologies used in distance learning, such as computers, have brought increasing benefits, such as cutting the cost of education and improving access to education technology in the classroom. However, teachers face the challenge of integrating educational technology into their daily work.

The ability of the World Wide Web inspired the creation of a new teaching model that incorporates the use of technological tools in the classroom. This model was named WebQuest, hereinafter WQ. In this paper, the researcher critically analyzes an approach to technology integration in English teaching through the design and use of a WebQuest and its influence on students' performance. To determine whether or not WebQuest can facilitate this is the thrust of this research effort.

Aim and objectives of the study

This study aimed to investigate the performance of students in morphology and syntax using the WebQuest design teaching strategy at Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to

1. The performance of male and female undergraduate students in morphology and syntax was examined using the WebQuest design teaching strategy.
2. Determine the interaction effect of gender and teaching methods on the mean morphology and syntax performance score of undergraduates.

Research questions

1. To what extent has the WebQuest design affected the morphology and syntax performance of male and female undergraduate students?
2. What is the interaction effect of gender and teaching methods on the mean morphology and syntax performance score of undergraduate students?

Hypotheses

H0₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students exposed to WebQuest.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in the interaction effect of gender and teaching method on the mean performance score of undergraduates in morphology and syntax in both the treatment (WebQuest) and control groups.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a quasi-experimental pretest and posttest non-equivalent group design.

The design is presented as follows:

Groups	Pre-Test	Treatment	Post-Test
E	01 X1 02		
C	03 -- 04		

Where:

- E = Experimental group
- C = Control (lecture method)
- XI = Treatment for the experimental group
- 01 = Pre-test for the experimental group
- 03 = Pre-test for control (lecture method)
- 02 = Post-test for the experimental group
- 04 = Post-test for control (lecture method)
- NO treatment

Area of study

The study was conducted in selected departments in the Faculty of Humanities, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The institution has seven departments. The faculty is headed by a dean, a professor of education. Every department is administered by a head who is also a professor or a senior lecturer in the department.

Population of the study

The study population consisted of 1,203 year two students in seven departments in the Faculty of Humanities, Ignatius Ajuru University, enrolled during the academic year of 2022/2023.

Sample and sampling techniques

Purposive sampling technique was used to select four departments from the population of 1,203 to obtain a sample of 2,808 year 2 undergraduate students that constituted the two non-equivalent intact classes that participated in the study using the following sampling criteria:

1. Departments where most students have Android phones/laptops that are internet compliant.
2. Departments where students have not been taught morphology and syntax.

The four departments that met the above sampling criteria were randomly assigned, two each to the experimental and control groups, using a simple random sampling technique.

Instruments for data collection

The instrument for data collection was a 40 (40) multiple-choice test on morphology and syntax (TOMAS) expected to measure the performance of undergraduate students in morphology and syntax.

Method of data collection

The instrument was administered to two groups as a pre-test for any existing differences in baseline knowledge and to ensure homogeneity in entry behavior. Their results were used as covariate measures. The students in the two groups were taught by lecturers assigned by the departments to teach the course using various techniques. The lecturers served as research assistants and were provided with detailed instructions on the conduct of learning activities and the lesson packages and learning instructions on morphology and syntax prepared by the researchers to ensure a uniform standard based on the course content. The experimental group was exposed to WebQuest design by using Android phones/laptops and the Internet. Provide appropriate and relevant resources/links that provide authentic learning tasks for students. The control group was taught the same content in Morphology and Syntax using the lecture method, which lasted for 3 months in a two-hour contact period as follows:

- Unit 1: Language Levels
- Unit 2: Morphology
- Unit 3: Syntax
- Unit 4: Comparison of morphology and syntax

Validity of the instrument

The original draft of the instrument was validated by one senior lecturer in language education and two experts in measurement and evaluation. Their feedback, contributions, comments, and corrections were incorporated into the final draft of the instruments, which were certified as adequate and valid for the study.

Reliability of the Instruments

A pilot study of the TOMAS was carried out on 20-year two undergraduate students of English Language within an interval of two weeks from the Faculty of Humanities of a non-participating university in the main study. Kuder-Richardson's formula, KR-21, was used to obtain a reliability index of 0.84 for the TOMAS.

Data Analysis Methods

Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and percentage, while analysis of variance and t-test were used to test the null hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Analysis

Results

Research Question One: To what extent has the WebQuest design affected the morphology and syntax performance of male and female undergraduate students?

H_{01} : No significant difference was found between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught with the WebQuest design.

Table 1: Mean, standard deviation, and t-test analysis of the effect of the WebQuest design on the academic performance of male and female students in morphology and syntax

Gender	n	Mean	Std. de	α	t-cal	sig.	Result	
Male	63	33.62	4.09	Insignificant				
				138	0.05	0.34	0.07	Accept Ho ₁
Female	77	33.83	3.35					

Table 1 shows that male undergraduate students had mean and standard deviation of 33:62 and 4:09, respectively, while females had mean of 33:83 and 3.35, respectively. The table reveals that male students had lower performance than female students. The calculated t-value was 0.34, which is greater than the 0.05 alpha level. Hence, since the sig. ($p = 0.07 > 0.05$) is higher than the 0.05 alpha, the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning that there is actually no significant difference between the performance of male and female undergraduates exposed to the WebQuest teaching strategy.

Research Question Two: What is the interaction effect of gender and teaching method on the mean morphology and syntax performance score of undergraduate students?

Ho₂: There was no significant difference in the interaction effect of gender and teaching method on the mean performance score of undergraduates in morphology and syntax in both the treatment (WebQuest) and control groups.

Table 2: Two-way ANOVA analysis of the effect of gender on the academic performance of undergraduate students in terms of morphology and syntax in both the treatment (WebQuest) and control groups

Group	Gender	N	\bar{p}	Std. D
WebQuest	Male	63	33.56	3.92
	Female	73	33.88	3.50
Total		170	33.73	3.69
Lecture Method	Male	58		15.87
	Female	82	14.29	4.54
Total		140	14.95	4.72
Total	Male	121	25.08	9.89
	Female	159	23.77	10.63

Source of sq.	Type IV sum de	Mean Sq	F	α	Sig.	Result	
Cor. Model	24792.45	3	8264.15	465.43	0.000	Insignificant	
Intercepts	163437.55	1	163437.55	9204.68	0.05	0.000	Accept Ho
Institution	23823.12	1	23823.12	1341.700	0.000		
Perception	27.19	1	27.19	1.53	0.22		
Error	4900.63	276	17.75				
Total	195614.00	280					
Cor. Total	29693.09	279					

Table 2 indicates that the mean and standard deviation scores for male and female students in the experimental group (WebQuest design) were 33.56 and 3.92 and 33.88 and 3.50, respectively. The control group (lecture method) had a mean and standard deviation of 15.87, 4.86, and 14.29, 4:54, respectively. From their mean, one could see that in the experimental group, female students outperformed male students, whereas in the control

group, male students performed better than female students. Their test of between-subject effects shows an interactive F of 3.54, while a sig. value of 0.06 was realized. Hence, since the sig ($P = 0.06 > 0.05$) is higher than the 0.05 alpha level, the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning that there is no significant difference in the interactive effect of gender on the morphology and syntax of undergraduate students in both the treatment (WebQuest) and control groups.

Discussion of the Findings

Performance of male and female students taught morphology and syntax using WebQuest

Finding three also revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students exposed to the WebQuest design at the pretest and protest levels. This means that in both groups, there is no significant difference in the performance of male and female students. The findings also revealed that both male and female students had a similar understanding of the subject. From the mean scores, it is revealed that in the pretest, both male and female students scored significantly and relatively lower. Also, in the post-test level, both male and female students performed significantly and relatively similar. This finding agrees with Tsai's (2006) finding that there was no significant difference in the performance of male and female students exposed to the WebQuest design.

Interaction of gender and teaching method on the mean performance score of undergraduate students in morphology and syntax

Finding from the interaction effect of gender on the mean morphology and syntax performance score of undergraduate students in both the treatment (WebQuest) and control group. No significant difference was observed in the interactive effect of gender on the academic performance of undergraduates in morphology and syntax in both the treatment (WebQuest) and control groups. This agrees with the research findings of Zacharia, xenofontos and Manoli (2011), who further confirmed insignificant differences in the performances of male and female students exposed to WebQuest design teaching strategy.

Conclusion

It is obvious that the WebQuest technique is one of the new innovations in education that aids in the teaching learning process. It is highly effective in improving students' academic performance, especially in morphology and syntax. Furthermore, students have a positive attitude toward the WebQuest technique, which is similar between male and female students. The WebQuest design was found to be effective, and the experimental group had a significant improvement in performance after being exposed to teaching. The package goes a long way in making the lesson more interesting and giving a better performance to the learners.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that morphology and syntax should be taught to undergraduate students using the WebQuest design teaching strategy because it enhances the performance of both male and female students.

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